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UVERENJA I STAVOVI PACIJENATA SA HRONIČNIM LUMBALNIM SINDROMOM: PILOT STUDIJA

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Uvod: Hronični lumbalni sindrom se definiše kao prisustvo bola u regiji između donje ivice poslednjih rebara i glutealne regije, sa/bez širenja bola duž donjih ekstremiteta, u trajanju dužem od 12 nedelja i jedan je od vodećih uzroka invaliditeta.

Cilj: Ispitati uverenja i stavove pacijenata sa hroničnim lumbalnim sindromom.

Materijal i metode: Retrospektivna studija preseka obuhvatila je 68 žena, starosti ≥ 40 godina, upućenih na pregled u Specijalnu bolnicu za reumatske bolesti Novi Sad, uz odobrenje Etičkog odbora ustanove. Dobijeni su podaci popunjavanjem sociodemografskog upitnika i dva upitnika za procenu uverenja i stavova pacijenata: Back Beliefs Questionnaire (BBQ) i The Pain Catastrophizing Scale (PCS). BBQ se sastoji od 14 stavki o mišljenju pacijenata o problemima sa donjim delom leđa procenjenih petostepenom Likertovom skalom. Veći ukupan skor ukazuje da ispitanik manje pokazuje strah i lažna uverenja. PCS je upitnik od 13 stavki podeljenih u tri supskale: ruminacija, preuveličavanje i bespomoćnost. Raspon skale kreće se 0–52, a viši skor ukazuje na višu katastrofizaciju.

Rezultati: U istraživanju je učestvovalo 68 žena, prosečne starosti $58,48 \pm 6,56$ godina, čiji se bol kod više od polovine (64,7%) javlja i pri mirovanju i pri radu. Prosečne vrednosti BBQ skale bile su $48,15 \pm 6,35$, što ukazuje na relativno realno mišljenje ispitanika o bolu u leđima, dok su u proseku rezultati na PCS iznosili $21,25 \pm 11,83$, što ukazuje na srednji nivo katastrofiziranja bola. Utvrđeno je da ispitanici istih opštih karakteristika i nivoa bola imaju slične misli o bolu u leđima ($p > 0,05$). Katastrofiziranje bola statistički je značajan prediktor misli o bolu ($p = 0,014$, $p < 0,05$). Preuveličavanje bola takođe je prediktor katastrofizacije bola ($p = 0,005$, $p < 0,05$), a i bespomoćnost utiče na katastrofizaciju bola ($p = 0,017$, $p < 0,05$).

Zaključak: Ispitanice sa lumbalnim sindromom imaju relativno realno mišljenje o bolu u leđima, a katastrofiziranje bola je statistički značajan prediktor misli. Preuveličavanje je najjači prediktor, sledi ukupna katastrofizacija bola i na kraju bespomoćnost.

Ključne reči: Lumbalni sindrom; uverenja; katastrofizacija.

BELIEFS AND ATTITUDES OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LUMBAR SYNDROME: A PILOT STUDY

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Introduction: Chronic lumbar syndrome is defined as the presence of pain in the region between the lower edge of the last ribs and gluteal region, with/without spreading pain along the lower extremities, lasting longer than 12 weeks. It is one of the leading causes of disability.

Aim: To examine the beliefs and attitudes of patients with chronic lumbar syndrome.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional study included 68 women, aged ≥ 40 , referred for examination to the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases Novi Sad, with approval of the institution's Ethics Committee. Data were obtained by filling out a socio-demographic questionnaire and two questionnaires assessing patients' beliefs and attitudes: the Back Beliefs Questionnaire (BBQ) and the Pain Catastrophizing Scale (PCS). The BBQ consists of 14 items assessing patients' opinions about lower back problems, rated on a five-point Likert scale. A higher total score indicates less fear and fewer false beliefs. The PCS is a 13-item questionnaire divided into three subscales: rumination, exaggeration, and helplessness. The scale ranges from 0 to 52, with higher scores indicating greater pain catastrophizing.

Results: The study included 68 women, with an average age of 58.48 ± 6.56 years. More than half (64.7%) experienced pain both at rest and during work. The average BBQ score was 48.15 ± 6.35 , indicating relatively realistic beliefs about back pain. The average PCS score was 21.25 ± 11.83 , indicating a moderate level of pain catastrophizing. Patients with similar general characteristics and pain levels had similar thoughts about back pain ($p > 0.05$). Pain catastrophizing was a statistically significant predictor of back pain beliefs ($p = 0.014$, $p < 0.05$). Pain exaggeration was also a predictor of pain catastrophizing ($p = 0.005$, $p < 0.05$), and helplessness influenced pain catastrophizing ($p = 0.017$, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Patients with lumbar syndrome generally have realistic beliefs about back pain. Pain catastrophizing is a significant predictor of beliefs, with exaggeration being the strongest predictor, followed by total pain catastrophizing and helplessness.

Keywords: lumbar syndrome; beliefs; catastrophizing